

Effect of Rock Phosphate on Setting Characteristics, Strength and Durability of Portland Cement

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Abstract

Portland cement is widely used and well known cement. The invention of Portland cement is credited to Joseph Aspdin in 1824 who patented an artificial cement made by calcination of argillaceous limestone. The name "Portland cement" was given originally due to the resemblance of the colour and quality of the hardened cement to Portland stone, a lime stone quarried in Dorset. The Portland cement was manufactured first in USA in 1872. It was manufacture in India in 1914.

Portland cement is manufactured by calcining calcium carbonate (as lime stone) grand together with aluminium silicates and other clays containing silica, alumina and iron oxide. Incorporation of some Inorganic and organic additives may increase then strength and durability of Portland cement. Incorporation of Glass powder as additive increases moisture resistance of the Portland cement in optimum proportion (20%) it increases strength and durability of the Portland Cement.

The effect on setting characteristics weathering characteristics, compressive strength and durability of Portland Cement studied by using some organic and inorganic additives.

Keywords Portland Cement, Compressive Strength, Linear Change, Magnesia Cement, Setting Time, Weathering Effect, Composition, Rock Phosphate.

Introduction

Introduction Chemical composition of rock phosphate (tricalciumphosphate) is $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$. It is found in nature in yellowish white colour. The mineral is brittle. Its hardness and density are approx. 5 and 3.2 respectively. Literature is silent about the effect of this material on setting and bonding characteristics of Portland cement. Rock phosphate is sparingly soluble mineral. The author thought that finally powdered rock phosphate may interact through its residual surficial valencies with active lime and othersiliceous materials to serve as an strength giving filler admixture. Hence it was tried as an admixture.

Aim of study

Portland cement is manufactured by calcining calcium carbonate (as lime stone) grand together with aluminium silicates and other clays containing silica, alumina and iron oxide. Incorporation of some Inorganic and organic additives may increase then strength and durability of Portland cement. Incorporation of Glass powder as additive increases moisture resistance of the Portland cement in optimum proportion (20%) it increases strength and durability of the Portland Cement.

Review of Literature

- i. Soluble phosphorus and acidic pH in phosphogypsum lead to significant delays in Portland cement setting time.
- ii. Alkaline phosphogypsum may be a substitute for natural gypsum in Portland cement.
- iii. Cement setting times were extended with P_2O_5 soluble from 0.33% to 1.32%.

2	5	236.100	227.850	225.500
3	10	233.100	228.350	226.250
4	15	237.020	228.400	225.900
5	20	240.200	231.850	229.400

1.3 Moisture Ingress Investigations:

All the setting investigation blocks after studying weathering effects were exposed to boiling water as per standard procedure. Relative water vapour transmission has been expressed as a function of time. The results are recorded in the Table 3.

Table 3 : Effect of Rock Phosphate on moisture ingress characteristics of portland cement.

Temperature - 27+1°C

Composition of dry-mix -1:4(w/w)

Relative humidity - above 80%

(Portland Cement : dust)

Quantity of dry-mix- 200 gm.

S.No.	% Additive	Trial locks kept in boiling water for (hrs.)					
		0-5	5-10	10-15	15-20	20-25	25-30
1	0	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
2	5	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
3	10	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
4	15	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
5	20	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE

NE: No Effect

1.4 Compressive Strength Investigations:-

The effect of Rock phosphate on compressive strength of Portland Cement compositions was studied by preparing standard sized trial blocks (70.6mm x 70.6 mm x 70.6 mm). Solid form of magnesium oxide was added in dry-mix in different proportions (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%) by weight of Portland cement. Thoroughly mixed 1:4 dry-mix with Rock Phosphate was gauged with water and filled into standard compressive strength testing moulds with surface area 50 cm. These moulds were kept under identical condition of temperature and relative humidity. Compressive strength of these blocks were determined as per IS specifications with the help of compressive strength testing machine. Experimental findings are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4 : Effect of Rock Phosphate on compressive strength of Portland cement.

Temperature - 27+1°C

Composition of dry-mix -1:4(w/w)

Relative humidity - above 80%

(Portland Cement : dust)

Quantity of dry-mix - 1000 gm.

S.No.	% Additive	Compressive strength (kg/cm ²)
1	0	200
2	5	210
3	10	160
4	15	140
5	20	120

1.5 Linear Change:

Investigation. amount just sufficient to obtain a plastic mass of IS consistency. Wet-mixes were then filled into standard sized moulds (200 mm x 25 mm x 25 mm) and kept under identical conditions of temperature and relative humidity. Linear changes in the beams so formed were determined as per IS specifications. Finding are summarised in the Table 5.

Table 5 : Effect of Rock Phosphate on linear change characteristics of Portland cement.

Temperature – 27+ 1°C

Composition of dry-mix -1:4(w/w)

Relative humidity - above 80%

(Portland Cement : dust)

Quantity of dry-mix- 200 gm.

S.No.	% Additive	Length of beams (mm)		Change in length (mm)
		Initial	Final	
1	0	200	200.28	0.28
2	5	200	201.01	1.01
3	10	200	201.52	1.52
4	15	200	201.61	1.61
5	20	200	201.67	1.67

Result and Discussion

The Table 1 summarises the effect of rock phosphate as a trial additive in varying proportions in wet mix on setting characteristics of Portland cement. It is noted that initial incorporation of rock phosphate increases initial as well as final setting periods (up to about 50%). On further admixing the additive setting periods decrease gradually, with increasing proportions of the additive. The plausible reason seems that rock phosphate has a tendency to absorb di or trivalent cations (Ca, Al etc.) to form insoluble crystalline phases. The removal of these active bond forming species in this way should hamper the kinetics of setting reactions. Accordingly, initial as well as final setting periods increase sharply. On further incorporation (beyond 5%) of the additive, it appears that reactions involving bond formation (exothermic) and formation of interlacing crystals of phosphates and aluminasilicates assist the setting process. Accordingly initial as well as final setting periods are found to decrease.

The Table 2 record the effect of rock phosphate on weathering characteristic of Portland cement. The observed results suggest that some uncombined moisture is left even after the final setting period. Accordingly gradual loss in weight with time of the

trial setting blocks due to slow evaporation of the uncombined moisture is quite expected.

The observed data of the Tables and the apparent look of the trial blocks after 30 days suggest that the additive has not caused any damaging effects on the blocks on ageing weathering. The above conclusions are substantiated from the moisture ingress characteristics of the trial blocks recorded in the Table 3. It is found that the trial blocks are not affected even after 30 hours of their exposure to steam. The moisture ingress is also found to be very insignificant.

The Table 4 reflects the effect of rock phosphate on compressive strength of the trial cubic block. It is observed that minor additions of the additive up to about 5% improve their structural or compressive strength. This appears to be due to inactivation of impurities of free active lime/alumina. Further incorporation of the additive is not favourable to the compressive strength. It may be attributable to the fact that phosphate ion being a bigger and less complex trivalent anion distorts the structural chains of the strength-giving compositions. Thus decreasing compressive strength with increasing amounts of the additive beyond a limit is quite expected. The trends are shown in the Table 4.

The data of the Table 5 pertaining to effect of rock phosphate on linear change characteristics of the standard blocks are in quite harmony with the observed compressive strength data. Thus it is noted that beyond 5% incorporation of the additive contributes to positive linear change for the reasons mentioned above. It is an established fact that linear change beyond 1.5 mm is harmful to the strength of the structure. Thus increasing linear change beyond 5%, incorporation of the additive results in decreasing compressive strength of the trial blocks.

- Conclusion**
1. Rock phosphate slows down setting process if incorporated up to 10%.
 2. Its incorporation up to about 5% is good for ultimate strength and durability of the product.
 3. If admixed in optimum proportions rock phosphate is better additive.

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